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EXPERIMENTATION IN CAR STYLING RESEARCH

THE MERITS OF STIMULI DESIGN AND EXPERIMENT DESIGN

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes the ongoing development of stimuli design in automotive form research, embedded in research into the meaning of automotive form. For experiments, in which images of cars are being compared, a number of stimuli representation and design issues are being raised and discussed.

The objective is to eliminate visual noise without compromising the observer's view. Issues that are being addressed include color, image backgrounds, viewing angle and display size.

The intermediate outcome of the research on automotive form has led to new stimuli design. A leap in reducing visual noise is to compare a car to an altered version of itself, rather than to another car. Background and possibly color become less important, since the two images are in essence the same.

Manipulating existing design though requires professional styling skills in preserving the coherency of the original styling and its leitmotiv, opening a whole new can of worms.

Keywords: car styling, meaning of form, design of stimuli.

INTRODUCTION

This paper describes the ongoing development of stimuli design in automotive form research. The meaning of automotive form is being researched in the Advanced Automotive Design specialization at Delft's faculty of Industrial Design Engineering. The research objective is not only to measure the impact of a design in terms of visual experience, but also to explain why.

Hence, the term 'stimuli' in this context refers to representations of cars in cognitive experiments. In order to observe and judge a car's complex form in a structured manner, an 'automotive form hierarchy' has been developed in Delft, to dismantle its form in isolated, assessable elements. For the design of stimuli though, it raises a range of issues, that may be considered of influence on the quality of experiment results.

In this paper the context by which the research on automotive form is inspired is being explained first. Next, the actual research is being described briefly in order to create some understanding on the stimuli that are needed. The merits of their design is being addressed twofold. Firstly, the design of the artifacts themselves, and secondly the merits of how to present them in the course of experiments.

CONTEXT

AUTOMOTIVE STYLING

The domain in which stimuli design, subject of this paper, takes place is that of automotive styling, or car styling. In this context the term 'styling' stands for is the integral form giving of cars, encompassing package design and negotiating with engineering constraints such as platform related dimensions, aerodynamics etc. In the automotive industry 'design' instead of 'styling' is used more often, because of 'styling's' incorrect superficial connotation (Bruens, 2007, Liem, 2009) which seems to imply styling as no more than a graphical touch. In this research the term 'styling' is maintained for clarity.

Automotive styling has been unable to adapt sufficiently to new project, product, and business paradigms (Anastakis, 2007).

Those new paradigms however, have a substantial impact on the automotive stylist's means to express a unique brand proposition through automotive form, the main styling concern in this context.

Automotive brand identities are generally embedded in 'brand owned' properties, e.g. safety, performance or reliability, which are in their turn often based on formerly 'brand owned' technologies (van Grondelle and van Dijk, 2004). These technologies and parts now have to be shared among the many, which leads to also sharing implicit form characteristics such as proportions, overhang and stance. Hence, those characteristics are largely eliminated from the stylist's vocabulary and means to create distinctive designs (Olsen, 2008).

In addition car companies are invading each other's historical domains (e.g. family cars, sports cars, mini's) as well as each other's geographical domains. This overflow of competitor's cars among which the stylist has to create a prominent, distinguishing car, coincides with the previously described decrease in true form drivers that would inspire that. To address this responsibility and contribute substantially to strategy formulation, implementation and realization (Person et al, 2007), styling must reposition itself in the value chain (de Wit and Meyer, 1994, and Porter, 2004).

THE STYLING PROCESS

A reflection on the automotive styling process, both through literature research as through authors' practice, shows that it has barely changed in the first century of the automobile. The tools have changed, especially through computer aided design (Tovey, 1994), but the decision making process has not. That is, the argument on form takes place around a number of consecutive manifestations of the design (sketches, scale models, full scale models...) and is largely based on tacit knowledge. A design proposal must nevertheless be founded on business arguments. An historical barrier, in the process of repositioning styling in the value chain, lies in cultural differences between styling an other, business or engineering focused disciplines (Gartman, 2004). There is no common frame of reference in place that links styling to other disciplines (van Grondelle, 2000, and Evans, Pei and Campbell, 2009).

This is expressed in earlier undertaken research on automotive form, in which cars are being assessed on the perceived meaning of their respective form. In those researches cars are assessed as a whole. Because of the complexity of automotive form however, no indication is given towards which form element or styling clue triggers that perception. In research that indeed does concentrate on specific form features, a very limited number of form features is being selected because of their perceived dominance in expressing a brand's identity, e.g. feature lines or the grill and headlights (Karjalainen, 2007, Chen et al, 2007).

RESEARCH ON AUTOMOTIVE FORM

To facilitate a more structured and integrated approach of automotive styling, methods and management models are being developed in the automotive research program at Delft University of Technology's faculty of Industrial Design Engineering. The explicit goal is to embed, foster and facilitate tacit knowledge, rather than compromising it, because its value in styling is undisputed in the industry.

The need for a structured assessment of automotive form became apparent with the development of a Branding Analysis Model (van Grondelle, 2000). The Automotive Form Hierarchy model (figure 1) aims to provide such a structured manner to assess automotive form, allowing for discussion on form, beyond subjective arguments.

Figure 1. Automotive Form Hierarchy model, 2nd version.

Such a management model, aiming to bridge a gap between disciplines, must contain familiar elements for each of those disciplines, a common vocabulary (Nonaka, 2000).

The left side of the hierarchy represents styling in a number of distinguishable drivers of automotive form. Those levels express technology and form philosophical choices (implicitly form constraints) and are linked to company levels on the right side of the model that represents the business side. The latter is of no relevance to the remainder of this paper.

STIMULI REPRESENTATION DESIGN

The experiments for which stimuli are being developed are generally of the same form. Participants are expected to respond to images of cars in comparison. They are asked to express their perception on form in terms that explain its meaning. The hierarchy allows to assess automotive form in a structured manner.

The objective in the design of stimuli is to reduce the differences between both the artifacts that need to be compared as well as the images thereof, to those properties that are the actual subject of comparison. Further differences are regarded as visual noise, that will obscure the comparison's outcome.

This is a generally accepted principle in automotive design environments. Different product appearances, like sketches and clay models, can not be compared. When equal appearances are not available, the objective is to adapt one artifact to the other. In order to compare a non-see-through clay model to an existing car the latter's green house may be treated with foil in order to blind its windows as well. Next to the equality of stimuli that are being compared, their detailing is equally important to the observer. The usage of simplified images, e.g. line drawings or simplified pictures, are a limitation of realism which also prevents the observers brand recognition and aesthetic preferences (Chen et al, 2007).

COLOR

As argued, the reduction of visual noise is crucial as to the reliability of the research outcome. In the earlier research on the brand portfolio analyses model it was decided to display all images in grey scale (Grondelle, 2000). The yet undisputed argument being that taking color out of the equation removes a dominant influence. Grey scale has been

applied to academic lecture materials ever since, its value being recognized in regular student evaluations.

It should be noted though that color may not be regarded as visual noise by default. Historically, racing car colors were related to their nationality. E.g. British racing Green (Andrews et al, 2005). Few car companies have adapted these national colors as their brand identity, like Ferrari's red. Color then becomes a brand aspect and the discarding thereof must be considered carefully.

Grey however is such a widely adopted color by all car makers throughout times and not bounded by short term fashion trends, that an effect of brand recognition by color does not occur.

Practically, the advantage is that transforming images to grayscale is available in most software and needs no specific skill.

Other researchers on the topic, mentioned in this paper, seem to concur and have also displayed their images in grey scale.

BACKGROUNDS

Backgrounds are also potential visual noise, but removing those is not without risk. Talke has, in the research towards newness in automotive form, compared competing cars of the same segment, using images of cars in which all backgrounds have been replaced by white (figure 2) (Talke, 2009). This results in 'floating' cars out of their natural context which may be perceived as uncomfortable and eligible to misinterpretation since context is an integral factor in understanding and valuing artifacts in cognition theory (Palmer, 1999, Solso, 2001). As a consequence, backgrounds play an implicit role in understanding product size.

In a more ideal situation cars may have been photographed at the same location. With equal backgrounds the perceived visual noise effect, in which the background influences the observers perception of the car, may be expected minimal. Practically this is difficult. Photography of all cars has to be arranged by the researcher with obvious logistic complexity.

Alternatively, adding the backgrounds digitally also requires specific skills in matching viewing angles and having the environment reflect correctly in the car's surfaces.

Figure 2. Cars without context and sense of scale. In the background the website questionnaire in which they are being displayed. Backgrounds have been removed, apart from a hint of shadow. Being displayed in small scale, a few centimeters each, and in different scales between, perception of the car's form is questionable.

POSITION

Various researchers state that a 3-quarter front view is considered ideal (Liem et al, 2009). This may be argued to be an understandable, but limited view. The understanding comes from architectural principles as already practiced in ancient Greece. The principle is also being practiced by automotive photographers. Articles in car magazines often display multiple images of car's (3 quarter) front and none of the rear.

One arguable reason is that the cars front (face) is generally the most recognizable in terms of character and brand identity. Tovey and Porter's research suggests the three quarter front view to be providing the strongest recognition of a car (Tovey and Porter, 2002).

Chen limits his stimuli to only four form features, all visible from the three quarter front view.

The chosen view however, must be suitable to express a product's scale and role (Solso, 2001, Eissen and Steur, 2009).

Considering the form hierarchy, it may be concluded that the view angle must be determined by the level of the form hierarchy which is being researched. If the experiment addresses e.g. a car's volume arrangement, a silhouette is most appropriate for that is where it is most visible. In figure 3 the Chrysler's leitmotiv (binding form principle that brings the overall styling into a whole, rather than a composition of individual forms) is referred to as 'cab forward'. The short nosed silhouette derives from the forward placed cabin (cab). The windscreen 'sits' on the firewall right above the middle of the front wheel. In a three quarter view this is hard to determine.

In general, having more views available (Talke, 2009) is desirable.

Figure 3. Appropriate view angle determination for Chrysler's cab forward volume arrangement.

ANIMATED STIMULI

It may be noted that practical considerations are, as with grey scale, very influential here. Animated views (e.g. a turntable) would be preferable above a range of stills. Rotating the car not only allows to assess its form from all angles.

It also allows to see reflections travel the surface, which is instrumental in car design (Liem et al, 2009). Practical complications however are twofold. Firstly a three dimensional cad model of each car in the research must be available. As well as expert knowledge to create the turntables.

Some car manufacturer's websites do provide hand driven turntables as part of their 'car configurators', in which the customer can create his own version of a car in terms of color and trim. They are however very different in representation and would, in experiments, limit the choice of stimuli to those manufacturers who provide this service.

REPRESENTATION SCALE

In most quantitative work on car styling the authors limit themselves to small images in order to assure practically (Person et al, 2008). The scale of representation of images must be appropriate for the artifact's scale, as well towards the observing conditions. In Person's research a small image scale may be considered acceptable because the sample existed of automotive professionals who only needed the images for reference.

However, to really distinguish form of a large object, a computer screen is considered to be too small. It is common knowledge amongst automotive stylists that a full scale model, derived directly from a CAD model (modeled on a computer screen) will show unexpected effects.

This is caused by the difference in assessment of form between the two differently sized media and requires long term experience of the stylist.

In automotive styling a scale of 1:5 is generally accepted as the smallest valuable scale to assess exterior styling models (Bertholon et al, 1988). It may be considered appropriate to hold on to that principle in displaying images as well (Eissen and Steur, 2009).

By the use of two projectors, images for comparison may be beamed on a wall in a size of around 80 cm which concurs with a scale of 1:5 to 1:4.

Chen approaches this, displaying the image of a single car full screen. In an educational environment in which students are to detect a car's leitmotiv, a similar scale is being appreciated while smaller scales (displaying two cars in a single beam) provoke complaints.

STIMULI ARTIFACT DESIGN

The previously discussed issues on color, position and context are aimed at reducing visual noise when comparing different cars, be it of a single brand or between competitors.

A further step in limiting visual noise is to compare cars not with others, but to altered version of themselves. We may then examine the emotional impact of single alterations to its form. It will allow to measure the perception of a car's form, e.g. greenness or sportiness, in the eye of the observer and more importantly identify the underlying reason (styling choice).

Stimuli have been designed that differ in only a few form elements at any relevant level of the form hierarchy, whereas the rest remains unchanged.

Figure 4. manipulated BMW (left) in comparison with the original

By the use of computer drawing programs, images of cars are easily manipulated. Any perceptual effects may then be related back to a few identifiable form elements.

Figure 4 shows a manipulated image of a BMW in comparison with itself. Preliminary studies on the usability thereof raised a number of issues concerning stimuli design, discussed hereafter.

THE STRENGTH OF A VISUAL BRAND IDENTITY

The original BMW (on the right) has a short front overhang (length between its front wheel and the foremost part of the car) because of the layout of its drive train. The wheel base (distance between the wheels in the car's length) of the BMW on the left in image 4 has been shortened. It may be expected that placing the front wheel backwards has an impact on its perceived character. E.g. the car may no longer be perceived as being fast.

When confronting observers with the image, results were minimal. Most observers noticed nothing. The perceived implication is that the change was not drastic enough. A number of issues have been raised. It may be considered undisputed that BMW has a strong visual identity (Grondelle, 2002). From any standpoint a BMW is recognized as that. In BMW's case this derives from form elements at all levels of the form hierarchy. It allows BMW to vary its styling in specific levels of the hierarchy because recognized features at other levels will preserve its overall perception.

That raises the question to what extent the design must be changed in order to get valuable information on the effects of form changes. Preliminary try-outs indicate that cars form brands with a strong visual brand identity need more drastic changes in order to be able to measure their effect.

Small changes were not perceived because the observer drew conclusions based on prior knowledge, familiar form and features, rather than from the observation itself (Hekkert, 1995). That may be valuable for brand identity research, but not for the purpose of the experiments at hand. Changes had to be more drastic before they were perceived.

THE ARCHETYPICAL CAR

In order to avoid problems as described in the previous paragraph, a different approach was initiated to measure the effects of single form manipulations on a car design.

The starting point was the design of an archetypical car. The underlying thought being that, from there, form aspects may be manipulated to see how it changes the viewer's perception of the car's characteristics, not influenced by the car's brand identity or the observer's knowledge.

The approach failed to provide valuable results. The reason is that, in an archetype too, every choice has meaning. Overhang, ratio, round offs, everything stands for something, and suggests a brand or model. Lowering the roofline makes a Chrysler, lengthen the rear and it becomes a Jaguar, (figure 5). There's arguably no such thing as a neutral archetype to start from.

APPLICATION OF A LEITMOTIV

A second problem with the manipulation of existing designs, is that in the styling process a leitmotiv is translated into an overall automotive form and translated coherently into its detailing, making the design into a whole.

Considering that definition, can we manipulate a single form element without compromising a car's leitmotiv, and therefore its form integrity?

Figure 5. the 'archetypical' car adapted to conventional Jaguar saloon styling clues in two variants

Figure 6. Toyota Prius with larger wheels en lengthened wheel base, versus the original on the left.

It may be argued that, if the altered form element would have been part of the original styling, as the lengthened overhang in the BMW example, than certainly the front panels and light units would have been designed differently as well. It seems therefore plausible that, next to changing the form element which is subject to the experiment, its surrounding must be considered for redesign too.

In figure 6 a Toyota has been modified with larger wheels and, as suggested, modified wheel arches to match. In this example those alterations are insufficient because they conflict with the character lines of the car, that now run right through the wheel arches, and the overall proportion of the car. That would imply these too need to be changed, leaving little to none standing of the original design. The question is how to compromise between safeguarding the leitmotiv, and changing as little as possible, in order to preserve the experimental outcome? A practical limitation in this is that the preservation of a car's form integrity requires styling skills.

CONSOLIDATION

CONCLUSIONS

The design of stimuli is an iterative process in which choices raise new issues that must be considered. By applying a number of principles to the representation of stimuli, early trials suggest better reliability of the outcome of experiments on the perception of the meaning of automotive form. These principles are the application of grey scale, the preservation of backgrounds and a minimal display size in scale of 1:4 in appropriate views.

The design of stimuli in manipulating automotive form requires styling skills in order to preserve a form's coherency and leitmotiv.

LIMITATIONS AND FURTHER RESEARCH

GREY SCALE

The use of images in grey scale has been identified as beneficial in the design of stimuli, or the making of lecturing materials on form. That may be so, but the objective of reducing noise does not automatically imply image transformation to grey scale. The choice for grey scale has also been made for practical reasons.

Images of cars in the same color, and preferably photographed in the same environment, may equally fulfill the objective of visual equality. An interesting experiment may be the application of sepia effect instead of grayscale, and measure the observer's perception towards the age of the depicted cars.

IMAGE BACKGROUNDS

Regarding earlier remarks on the advantage of equal backgrounds in compared images, a similar principle may be applied to the image's background. In the comparison between a car that may be perceived as fast, and one that may be perceived as slow, a background of trees may inspire another experiment outcome than a racing track.

MOVING STIMULI

The usage of multiple views aligns with different display needs for different levels of the hierarchy, as well with the notion that brand recognition must be present in any view.

Still, multiple views are a limitation compared to animated images, e.g. turntable. Further research into the practical implications in providing these is foreseen.

EXPERIMENTAL CONDITIONS

Further research addresses experimental conditions. Should experiment participants manage the duration, in which images are showed, themselves, or must it be regulated? If so, what would be the appropriate display duration? Will various display times lead to another research outcome?

FINAL STIMULI

The final stimuli design is to be determined in terms of styling detail in relation to a brand's visual identity. The rejected idea of the neutral archetype, may still be of value because it raised the issue of the required, or essential, level of detail.

Limiting the number of grey tones may reduce visual noise and simplify an image to its true merits, much like when designers assess a form by looking through their eye lashes.

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